

EFFECT OF SKIN INTEGRITY BUNDLE APPLICATION ON PRESSURE ULCER OCCURRENCE FOR PATIENTS IN CRITICAL CARE UNITS

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Abstract

Background: Pressure ulcers (PUs) have been identified as a worldwide problem that contribute significantly to increasing health care costs, compromise an individual's health, and in some cases contribute to mortality. Generally, PUs is considered predictable and preventable, thus making them a priority patient safety and risk management issue. **Aim:** This study aimed to find out the effect of skin integrity care bundle on patient pressure ulcer occurrence in the critical care unit. **Design:** Quasi-experimental research design (study & control group) was carried out to meet the aim of this study. **Setting:** This study was conducted in the intensive care units at Sabya General hospital (SGH), Gizan, south region of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). **Subject:** Purposive samples of 120 adult patients were divided into two equal groups; the control group and the study group with 60 patients in each group of both genders. **Data collection tools:** Data were obtained using three tools; Patient assessment record, Pressure ulcer staging and the Braden Scale score. **Results.** The results reveals that the highest percentage of subjects their age more than 60 years. In addition, 56.7% of study group & 66,7% of control group subjects were males. There was statistical significant difference between study and control group after the skin care bundle application regarding pressure ulcer stage ($p=0.047$), mobility ($p=0.02$), nutrition (0.02). Also, the total Braden scale reveals a statically significant difference between study and control group at one and two weeks after admission **Conclusion:** this study concluded that skin integrity care bundle had a positive effect in preventing the development of pressure ulcer of patients in critical care unit. **Recommendations:** Hospitals' policy should enforce the application of skin integrity bundle to prevent the occurrence of pressure ulcer. Also, motivate critical care nurses to attend conferences and workshops to update their knowledge and practice regarding the application of skin integrity bundle.

Keywords: Pressure Ulcer, Skin Integrity Bundle, Critical Care.

INTRODUCTION

Pressure ulcers (PUs) are one of the most common problems in health care settings. Hospitalized patients are often particularly vulnerable because of their illness. Literature suggests that PUs have devastating effects on patients' care outcomes, either on an individual patient or healthcare system. Outcomes of patients' level such as, quality of life, pain, infection, length of stay, morbidity and mortality. Outcomes of the healthcare system levels such as, quality of care and economic cost (**Sullivan, 2017**).

The term “pressure ulcer” is used throughout this document in lieu of “pressure injury”. There is a view that the term pressure injury is more realistic, as it denotes damage from pressure as an injury, possibly a preventable occurrence, whereas the term ulcer connotes a wound occurring as a complication of an event (**Australian Wound Management Association (AWMA), 2012**).

Pressure ulcer (PU) prevalence data vary widely across both settings and country. Prevalence rates have been reported at 3–26% in North America, 8.1–49% across Europe, 3–50% in Australia 7–44.4% in the Middle East 2.1–31.3% in Asia and 9.7–51.6% in Africa. Furthermore, PU incidence data also vary by clinical setting: In long-term care, from 2.3% to 23.9%; in acute care, from 0.4% to 38.6%; in home care, from 0% to 17% and in rehabilitative care, from 0% to 6%. However, data highlight that intensive care units (ICUs) have the highest PU incidence rates in health care settings, which have been reported as high as 50% (**Mervis et al., 2019**).

Critically ill patients in Intensive care unit (ICU) may experience multiple physiological changes directly related to their illness and possibly their care. The majority of ICU patients are ventilated, sedated, therefore, unable to care for themselves, unable to move or change position. Further, the patient’s critical illness may involve hemodynamic instability which potentially may complicate and accelerate the effects of prolonged immobility. Paradoxically, mobility is a natural defense to alleviate prolonged pressure on the skin (**Shahin et al., 2008**).

Extensive exposure to pressure, from lying or sitting on a specific part of the body renders patients at greater risk of skin breakdown. Therefore, the vulnerability of these patients places them at high risk of impaired skin integrity, particularly pressure ulcer development (**Bouten et al., 2015**).

The term “care bundle approach” refers to a set of three to six treatment interventions targeted towards a specific procedure, symptom, or treatment (**Cinel et al., 2016**). **Robb et al. (2017)** argued that the care bundle approach is more effective than simply following clinical guidelines. This may be due to the mandatory and audited nature of care bundles, whilst clinical guidelines are regarded as advisory.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

PU is recognised as potentially preventable conditions; however, their epidemiological rate of occurrence is still alarming. Literature suggests that this problem is underreported, particularly in the KSA, and that there is a lack of awareness concerning PU prevention and management through the health care systems (**Anthony, Parboteeah, Saleh, & Papanikolaou, 2017**). The International Pressure Ulcer Prevalence Survey indicated that facility-acquired pressure ulcer prevalence rates were highest (12.1%) in the ICU. According to ministry of health of Saudi Arabian reported that about acute care pressure ulcer prevalence of 44.4% and incidence of 38.6% (**Saleh, 2018**). There is a relationship between pressure ulcer and increased morbidity and mortality rates because Pressure ulcer can also lead to serious infectious

complications, like bacteremia, septicemia and wound infection. So, Pressure ulcers requiring specialized nursing intervention for patients in Critical Care Units. This research is significant because it is the first study of its kind to test the effectiveness of a PU prevention bundle, combining the best available evidence to improve critically ill patients' skin integrity in the KSA. Also, this research provided a novel approach to enhancing PU prevention in intensive care to reduce the incidence of PU development or delay the occurrence of PUs in the context of Saudi Arabian critically ill patients. Further, this study increases knowledge and awareness of nurses regarding PU prevention and management to enable nurses to provide high quality nursing care. Moreover, this study can be considered a reliable benchmark that will enable comparison with other PU studies in ICU contexts. **(Alshahrani et.al, 2021).**

Aims of the study:

This study aimed to find out the effect of skin integrity care bundle occurrence in the intensive care unit.

Research hypothesis

To fulfill the aim of the study the following research hypothesis were formulated:

Application of skin integrity bundle will have significant positive effect occurrence of patients in critical care unit.

Operational definition:

The Skin Integrity Bundle is a set of evidence-based interventions designed to maintain and protect skin health, primarily aimed at preventing pressure injuries (bedsores), skin breakdown, and other related complications in at-risk patients. outcome measures that are an integral part of an investigator's evaluation and selection of appropriate measures include reliability and validity.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Research design:

Quasi-experimental research design was carried out to meet the aim of this study. It is a kind of study that rigidly follows a scientific research design. It involves testing or attempting to prove a hypothesis by way of experimentation. It uses one or more independent variables, manipulating them and then using them on one or more dependent variables **(White et al., 2017).**

Setting:

This study was conducted in the intensive care units at Sabya General hospital (SGH), Gizan, south region of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). Hospital established in 2005. The hospital is operated by the Ministry of Health, KSA. It is major care hospitals, with over 250 beds and ambulatory services. Furthermore, facilities are accredited as meeting the national standards of excellence in quality and patient safety care and

health services by the KSA National Accreditation program, as determined by the Central Board of Accreditation for Healthcare Institution (CBAHI).

Intensive Care Unit is located in the first floor and consists of 12 beds in a single room, isolation room has one bed with negative pressure, manger offices, physician room, nurses' room, control patients' desk, supplies store, two bathrooms and 21 lockers for nurses.

Sampling:

A purposive sample of 120 adult patients were divided into two equal groups; the control group and the study group with 60 patients in each group of both gender. The sample size was calculated statistically by power analysis considering the total number of patients admitted to the intensive care units at Sabya General Hospital during the period (2023). The sample size was calculated by adjusting the power of the test to 80% and the confidence interval of 95% with margin of error accepted adjusted to 5% and a known total population of 120 patients. The sample was calculated according to the following equation: **Steven, (2012)**

$$n = [DEFF * Np(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z^2(1-\alpha/2)^2(N-1) + p*(1-p))]$$

DEFF (Design effect) = 1

N (population) = 100

p (Hypothesized %) = 10% +/- 5

d (tolerated margin of error) = 0.05

Z (level of confidence) = 1.96 α (Alpha) = 0.05

$$n = [1 * 100 * 10\% \pm 5 (1 - 10\% \pm 5)] / [(0.05)^2 / (1.96)^2 - 0.05 * (100 - 1) + 10\% \pm 5 (1 - 10\% \pm 5)]$$

Inclusion criteria:

Patient aged 18 years or more, admitted to the ICU during the study period and expected to stay more than 48 hours, free from PU.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients were excluded if they admitted to the ICU with a community-acquired PU, diagnosed with any stage of PU in the first 24 hours of admission to ICU and had medical contraindications for the implementation of the care bundle intervention (e.g., patients with a fractured pelvis or burns whose care could not follow the repositioning schedule).

Tools for data collection:

Three tools were utilized to collect data in this study.

Tool (I): Patient assessment record:

It was developed by the researcher after reviewing recent related literature included two parts (**Fathy et al., 2022, Niezgod, 2016 & Berlowizez, 2014**).

Part I: Demographics data included age, gender and nationality

Part II: Clinical data included Type of admission, mechanical ventilation (yes/no), length of time in OR, length of time in ER, weight, duration of mechanical ventilation, length of ICU stays, diagnosis and ICU outcome (discharged to the ward or died).

Tool (II): Pressure ulcer staging.

Pressure ulcer assessment stages: It included four stages (I, II, III, & IV). Where "I" means non-blanchable erythema, with intact skin surface; II means epithelial damage, abrasion or blister; III means damage to the full thickness of the skin without a deep cavity and IV means damage to the full thickness of the skin with deep cavity.

Additionally, as well as with PU staging, the PU site will identify on the data collection form by drawing a circle over the relevant area in the body figure. **NPUAP & EPUAP (2009).**

Tool (III): The Braden Scale score

This scale was adopted from **Smith et al (1995)**. It is a well-recognized, widely used and validated score for predicting risk of PU development. Accordingly, it consists of six elements: sensory perception; moisture; activity; mobility; nutrition; and friction and shear. Each subscale is rated numerically. While the first five elements are rated from 1 (most impaired) to 4 (least impaired), the last item "friction and shear" is rated from 1 (problem) to 3 (no problem). The total score ranges from 6 to 23, is calculated by adding the scores for each of the subscales; the lower the number, the higher the risk.

A total score between 15 and 18 indicates a low risk, a total score between 13 and 14 a moderate risk, a total score between 10 and 12 a high risk, and a total score under 9 a very high risk

Skin integrity care bundle: It was adopted from the Pan Pacific Pressure Injury Alliance, the European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel, and the National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel **Kottner et al., (2019)**. On the patients in the study group, it was employed to carry out the intended care. It consists of five key components: supporting the body surface, checking the skin, moving about and repositioning, caring for incontinence, nourishment and hydration, and taking preventive skin care measures.

PROCEDURES

Ethical considerations

The research approval obtained from the faculty of nursing ethical committee before starting the study. The researcher clarified the objectives and aim of the study to patients included in the study before starting. Researcher assured the anonymity and confidentiality of the patients included in the study.

The studied patients informed that they are allowed to choose to participate or not in the study and they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time.

Operational design:

The Preparatory phase: It includes reviewing of related recent literatures and theoretical knowledge of various aspects of the study using books, articles, internet search, periodicals and magazines to develop tools for data collection. outcome measures that are an integral part of an investigator's evaluation and selection of appropriate measures include reliability and validity, Reliability is the degree to which a score or other measure remains unchanged upon test and retest.

Validity and Reliability of the study tools

Validity testing ascertained by a group of three experts from Critical Care Nursing department at Faculty of Nursing at Ain Shams University (two professors and one assistant professors), to test its face and content validity. The jury reviewed the tools for objectivity, comprehensiveness, clarity, relevance and simplicity.

Reliability of the study tool: Content reliability of tools was confirmed for consistency by using Cronbach's alpha test. The tools proved to be reliable (0.82).

Pilot study:

A pilot study carried out on 10% of sample size (2) to test feasibility of the research process, applicability, clarity and efficiency of the tools. No radical modifications were done according to result of pilot study; participants involved in the pilot study were included in the study sample.

METHODS FOR DATA COLLECTION

The study was conducted through three main phases as following.

Preparatory phase:

This phase was through reviewing of related recent literatures and theoretical knowledge of various aspects of the study using books, articles, internet search, periodicals and magazines to develop tools for data collection.

Informed consent was obtained from the head of the intensive care unit.

Field of work:

The study was carried out through four phases: assessment, planning, implementation, and evaluation. These phases were carried out from beginning of February 2023 until the end of August.

Phase I. Assessment phase

- During assessment phase the researcher was prepared tools for date collection.
- The researchers assessed the patients for (risk assessment, skin assessment, nutrition, repositioning and support surfaces) who were received the standard PU prevention care for control group and The PU prevention bundle for study group.
- Assessment was done from the first day of admission until discharge. consequent

assessment tools sheet was used the demographic data, clinical data, SOFA score, Braden Scale and PU staging.

- All ICU RNs were informed about the PU prevention bundle through in-service, meetings, and one-to-one bedside education, all provided by the researcher. The training and education program consisted of: 1) brochures that explained the elements of the PU prevention bundle 2) a PowerPoint presentation with a handout used during in- service; 3) consultation and clarification on an individual basis with the researcher throughout the study.
- Regarding demographic and clinical data, it assessed by the researcher, the time needed to fill the questionnaire ranged from five to seven minutes. As well as, the pressure ulcer stage assessment ranged from 8-10 minutes to fill out. Regarding Braden Scale also it was assessed by researcher. The time needed to fill the scale ranged from 10-15 minutes. All patients were followed every two days from admission to discharge.
- The researcher provide care and organized all materials that required for the study group which included gentle wash gauze, nonirritant soap, skin moisturizer, a barrier product, air mattresses, small pillows that were applied on high-risk body parts of the skin such as heels and sacrum.

Phase II. Planning phase:

Based on the needs identified in the assessment phase from the participated patients in view the literature. The researcher determined the intervention protocol

Phase III. Implementation phase

1. Comprehensive Risk Assessment

- Conduct an initial risk assessment using tools such as the Braden Scale.
- Reassess daily and after any significant change in the patient's condition (e.g., hemodynamic instability).
- Focus on high-risk patients, such as those on mechanical ventilation, sedation, or receiving vasopressors.

2. Frequent Skin Inspection

- Inspect the skin at least once per shift, focusing on areas prone to breakdown (sacrum, heels, elbows, occiput, and areas under medical devices).
- Document and report any early signs of skin damage (erythema, blanching, or moisture lesions).

3. Pressure Redistribution

- Use specialized support surfaces such as alternating- pressure mattresses.
- Reposition patients every 2 hours, even if they are sedated or on mechanical

ventilation.

- Offload pressure from heels using heel suspension boots or pillows.
- Avoid placing patients directly on medical devices like oxygen masks or tubing; pad or reposition as necessary.

4. Moisture Management

- Protect the skin from excessive moisture caused by incontinence, perspiration, or wound drainage.
- Apply moisture barrier creams and use incontinence products designed to wick away moisture.
- Use intermittent urinary catheters and fecal management systems when appropriate to reduce prolonged moisture exposure.

5. Optimize Nutrition and Hydration

- Collaborate with a dietitian to provide adequate calories, protein, and essential nutrients.
- Administer enteral or parenteral nutrition for patients unable to eat orally.
- Monitor hydration levels and ensure fluid balance is maintained.

6. Medical Device Management

- Regularly check and adjust medical devices (e.g., endotracheal tubes, cervical collars, or restraints) to prevent device-related pressure injuries.
- Use foam dressings or silicone padding under devices to reduce friction and pressure.

7. Education and Communication

- Train critical care nurses and staff on early detection and intervention strategies for skin integrity.
- Promote clear communication among the healthcare team about skin care plans and risk status.

Phase IV. Evaluation phase:

Throughout this phase using the post-Comprehensive skin assessment and the Braden risk assessment scale, the researchers evaluated each patient in the control groups post receiving routine care pressure ulcer staging and also the study group were evaluated post receiving pressure ulcer prevention bundle to estimate the effect of implementing the nursing cluster pressure ulcer prevention bundle, on prevention of pressure ulcer for the study group.

Statistical analysis:

The collected data organized, categorized, tabulated and statistically analyzed using the statistical package for social science using SPSS program version 27. Quantitative data were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD). Qualitative data were presented as frequencies and percentages (%). Independent samples t-test (Student t test) was used to compare quantitative data between two independent groups. Chi square test (or Fisher Exact test) were used to compare qualitative data between different groups. The observed differences and relations were considered as follows: $P > 0.05$ in significance (No difference), $P \leq 0.05$ significance difference and $P \leq 0.001$ highly significance difference data. P-value was considered statistically significant at $P \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table (1): shows no statistically significant difference between the control and study group as regard age, gender and nationality at $p > 0.05$. The mean age in control group was 49.03 ± 22.95 and 51.12 ± 22.30 in the study group.

Regarding age groups; 31.7% of control group compare to 35% of the study group were aged more than 60 years.

In relation to gender 56.7% of the control compared to 66.7% of study group were males. Regarding nationality, 73.3% of control group and 63.3% of study group were Saudi.

Table (2): reveals that, there was statistically significant difference between control and study group as regards type of admission, length of time in the OR and weight at $P < 0.05$.

Table (3) show that, there was statically significance difference regarding stages at $P < 0.05$. But there was no statistically significant difference between both groups as regarding pressure ulcer occurrence and pressure injury area at $P > 0.05$.

Table (4) represent that, there was statistically significant difference as regard mobility and nutrition.

Table (5) illustrate that there was none statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding Braden scale on admission.

But there was statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding Braden scale from 1st week and two weeks post application $P < 0.05$.

Table (6) Clarifies that there was a statistically significant difference between study and control group after intervention as regard mean and SD of predicting pressure ulcer risk with p-value < 0.05 . considered statistically significant at $P < 0.05$

Table (1): Comparison between study group and control group regarding demographic data.

		Group				t*	P value
		Control group (N=60)		Study group (N=60)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Age		49.03	22.95	51.12	22.30	0.50	0.62
		N	%	N	%	X ^{2**}	P value
Age	18-30	20	33.3	14	23.3	1.75	0.78
	31-40	8	13.3	9	15.0		
	41-50	6	10.0	6	10.0		
	51-60	7	11.7	10	16.7		
	>60	19	31.7	21	35.0		
Gender	Male	34	56.7	40	66.7	1.27	1.23
	Female	26	43.3	20	33.3		
Nationality	Saudi	44	73.3	38	63.3	1.39	0.24
	Non-Saudi	16	26.7	22	36.7		

*Student t test **Chi square test

Table (2): Comparison between study group and control group regarding clinical data.

		Group				X ^{2***}	P value
		Control group (N=60)		Study group (N=60)			
		N	%	N	%		
Type of admission	Emergency	52	86.7	43	71.7	7.2	0.03
	Elective	3	5.0	13	21.7		
	Post-op	5	8.3	4	6.7		
Mechanical ventilation	No	27	45.0	24	40.0	0.31	0.57
	Yes	33	55.0	36	60.0		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	P value
Length of time in OR		43.33	27.24	65	41.9	16.5	0.017
Length of time in ER		95.8	86.5	88.66	58.7	133	0.95
Weight (kg)		62.67	9.05	68.92	12.14	3.20	0.001
Duration of MV		6.12	7.00	4.87	6.37	-1.02	0.3
Length of ICU stay		7.83	7.35	6.88	6.44	-0.75	0.45
Diagnosis		N	%	N	%	X ^{2***}	P value
Cardiovascular		4	6.7	6	10.0	8.14	0.42
Respiratory		11	18.3	10	16.7		
Renal		5	8.3	4	6.7		
Cerebrovascular		7	11.7	5	8.3		
DM-HTN		5	8.3	9	15.0		
Mental disorder		8	13.3	3	5.0		
Trauma		7	11.7	10	16.7		
DKA		11	16.7	6	11.7		
Liver		2	3.3	7	11.7		

Table (3): Comparison between study group and control group regarding pressure ulcer staging (n= 120)

		Group				X ^{2*}	P value
		Control group (N=60)		Study group (N=60)			
		N	%	N	%		
Pressure ulcer	No	53	88.3	57	95.0	0.44	0.51
	Yes	7	11.7	3	5.0		
Pressure injury area	Sacral area	5	71.4	2	66.6	2.05	0.67
	Buttocks	2	28.6	1	33.3		
	Shoulder	0	0	0	0		
	Occiput	0	0	0	0		
	wrist	0	0	0	0		
	Elbow	0	0	0	0		
Stages	Stage I	1	14.3	2	66.7	0.08	0.047
	Stage II	6	85.7	1	33.3		

Table (4): Comparison between study group and control group regarding Braden scale (n= 120)

		Group				X ^{2**}	P value
		Control group (N=60)		Study group (N=60)			
		N	%	N	%		
Sensory	Completely limited	24	40.0	36	60.0	5.80	0.12
	Very limited	6	10.0	3	5.0		
	slightly limited	19	31.7	16	26.7		
	No impairment	11	18.3	5	8.3		
Moisture	Constantly moist	3	5.0	1	1.7	3.07	0.38
	Often moist	17	28.3	11	18.3		
	Occasionally moist	29	48.3	33	55.0		
	Rarely moist	11	18.3	15	25.0		
Activity	Bed fast	7	11.7	15	25.0	5.59	0.13
	Chair fast	17	28.3	16	26.7		
	Walk occasionally	28	46.7	18	30.0		
	Walk frequently	8	13.3	11	18.3		
Mobility	Completely immobile	3	5.0	14	23.3	9.64	0.02
	Very limited	11	18.3	11	18.3		
	Slightly limited	35	58.3	23	38.3		
	No limitation	11	18.3	12	20.0		
Nutrition	Very poor	2	3.3	1	1.7	9.20	0.02
	Probably inadequate	7	11.7	14	23.3		
	Adequate	26	43.3	34	56.7		
	Excellent	25	41.7	11	18.3		
Friction	Problem	7	11.7	6	10.0	0.85	0.65
	Potential problem	23	38.3	28	46.7		
	No apparent problem	30	50.0	26	43.3		

Table (5): Comparison of study and control group regarding of total Braden scale on admission, 4th day, one week and two weeks after admission

Braden scale on admission pre	No risk	16	26.7	10	16.7	1.88	0.75
	Mild risk	24	40.0	28	46.0		
	Moderate risk	11	18.3	12	20.0		
	High risk	6	10.0	6	10.0		
	Severe risk	3	5.0	4	6.7		
4th day	No risk	10	16.6	15	25	3.722	0.293
	Mild risk	26	43.3	25	41.6		
	Moderate risk	13	21.6	11	18.3		
	High risk	7	11.6	5	8.3		
	Severe risk	4	6.6	4	6.6		
1st week	No risk	8	13.3	25	41.6	13.7	0.007
	Mild risk	25	41.6	20	33.3		
	Moderate risk	14	23.3	8	13.3		
	High risk	8	13.3	4	6.6		
	Severe risk	5	8.3	3	5		
2nd week	No risk	6	10.0	35	58.3	14.3	0.004
	Mild risk	25	41.6	17	28.3		
	Moderate risk	14	23.3	5	8.3		
	High risk	9	15	2	3.3		
	Severe risk	6	10	1	1.6		

Table (6): Comparison between study group and control group toward Mean and SD of predicting pressure ulcer before and risk score after skin integrity care bundle application (n= 120)

Item	Control group	Study group	P-value
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	
Before intervention	15.20 \pm 3.37	16.22 \pm 3.85	0.13
After intervention	15.20 \pm 3.67	19.19 \pm 2.6	0.003

DISCUSSION

Pressure ulcers (PUs) have been identified as a worldwide problem that contribute significantly to increasing health care costs, compromise an individual's health, and in some cases contribute to mortality. Generally, PUs are considered predictable and preventable, thus making them a priority patient safety and risk management issue (**Bauer et al., 2016**). Furthermore, a pressure ulcer is a main problem in nursing care, has a significant impact on the health care system, reduces the quality of life, exposes the patient to additional, complicates the patient's health condition, and is associated with a poor outcome in the ICU (**Al-Dorzi, 2019**). Care bundles are a set of nursing interventions, each part of which had been proven in clinical practice to improve patient outcomes. Previous studies had shown that care bundles introduce new nursing concepts and develop targeted nursing interventions that are tailored to patients with pressure ulcers, which contribute to the improvement of quality of life (**Mao and Zhu, 2021**). Care bundles were applied in patients with pressure ulcers with satisfactory

results (**Gilde et al., 2018**). The present study aimed to find out the effect of skin integrity care bundle on patient occurrence in the intensive care unit.

Demographic characteristics.

Two matched groups were recruited for this study, there were no statistically significant differences between the groups regarding their demographic characteristics.

The results of the present study reveal that, the mean age was 49.03 ± 22.95 in control group and 51.12 ± 22.30 in the study group; from the researcher point of view, it is may be due to decrease skin elasticity. this finding is consistent with **Mobed et al., (2022)** in study entitled "Effect of skin integrity care bundle on hospital acquired pressure ulcer among patient with traction". who found that the mean age of the study group was 36.4 ± 12.3 and 41.27 ± 13.6 in control group?

In relation to gender, the current study shows that nearly half of control group and two thirds of study group were male. From the researcher point of view this finding might be due to the fact that males constituted the majority of this study sample or may males be greater risk for pressure ulcer. This finding is agreement with finding of **Mao and Zhu, (2021)** in study entitled "The prevalence and specific characteristics of hospitalised pressure ulcer patients: A multicentre cross-sectional study" who found that two thirds of the observation group and sixty of control group were male.

Regarding nationality, results of the current study shows that the majority of the study populations were Saudi. From the researcher point of view this finding may be due to research setting.

Clinical data

Results of the current study shows that the majority of the study population was in emergency with statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding type of admission. From the researcher point of view, it is may be due the population culture. This finding goes in the same line with **Tervo-Heikkinen et al., (2023)** in study entitled " Interventions in preventing pressure injuries in acute inpatient care: A cross-sectional national study" who stated that more than half of the PU group and half of non- PU group was in emergency with statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding type of admission.

Results of the current study shows that more than one third of patients in the control and study group experienced mechanical ventilation. From the researcher point of view, it is may be due to 35% of patient had respiratory problem, 28% trauma and 16.7% cardiovascular issue. This result agrees with that of **Tayyib et al., (2015)** who reported that more than two third of control study group experienced mechanical ventilation. Also, this finding was supported by **Manzano et al., (2010)**. In study entitled "Pressure ulcer incidence and risk factors in ventilated intensive care patients" patients who require MV make them especially susceptible to the development of PUs, including mobility limitations; loss of sensory perception due to sedation and analgesia;

maceration of skin due to incontinence, sweating, or leaking wounds; and frequent hemodynamic and oxygenation disorders.

Regarding length of time in operation room current study reveals that statistically significant difference between control and study group. Regarding length of time in emergency room current study revealed that no statistically significant difference between control and study group. From the researcher point of view, it is may be due to small sample size.

Regarding weight our study shows statistically significant difference between control and study group. From the researcher point of view this finding may be due to increase level of education affect level of health. This result agreed with **Hyun et al., (2015)** who reported statistically significant difference between patients with PU and control group due to their heavy body weight and immobility, obese persons may be prone to pressure ulcers, which usually develop when body weight presses skins and tissues on to surfaces such as beds for long periods.

Our study findings show no statistically significant difference between control and study group as regards mean duration of MV 6.12 ± 7.00 in control group and 4.87 ± 6.37 in study group. From the researcher point of view, it is may be due to prolonged immobility and patients' conditions. This finding is supported by **Sayed and Sliman, (2021)**. In study entitled "Effect of Implementing Nursing Cluster Bundle on Prevention of Pressure Ulcer among Critically Ill Patients" who found that the mean duration of ICU stay was 4.75 ± 1.41 in the study group and 6.44 ± 2.97 in control group with statistically significant difference between both groups ($p=0.012$).

Results of the present study shows no statistically significant difference between control and study group as mean length of stay 7.83 ± 7.35 in control group and 6.88 ± 6.44 in the study group ($p=0.45$). From the researcher point of view, it is may be due the sign of an underlying disease, leading to an increased risk of complications This result agrees with that of **Tayyib et al., (2015)** who reported that the mean length of ICU stay was 10.4 ± 7.69 in control group and 11.2 ± 8.8 in study group with statistically significant difference between both groups ($p=0.928$).

As regarding diagnosis, the present study results shows that respiratory disease 18.3% in control group and 16.7% in study group, trauma 11.7% and 16.7% in study group and 16.7 cardiovascular disease, were the most common. From the researcher point of view, it is may be due to decrease a level of weariness and unhealthy life style. This finding goes in the same line with **Hyun et al., (2013)** In study entitled "Enhancing Intervention Fidelity: A Means of Strengthening Study Impact" who reported that the most frequent admission diagnoses were acute respiratory failure 8.1%. This finding disagreed with **Tayyib et al., (2015)** who found that trauma was the most common diagnosis in control group 12.9% and in the study group 24.3% with statistically significant difference between both groups.

Pressure ulcer

Regarding pressure ulcer current study shows those pressure ulcers were found more in control rather than study group. From the researcher point of view, it is may be due to did not properly care for their skin cleaning, drying and repositioning. This finding is supported by that of **Coyer et al., (2015)** who found that cumulative incidence of pressure injuries was significantly lower in the intervention group than in the control group.

Regarding pressure injury areas in current study were at sacral area followed by the buttocks in control and study groups with no statistically significant difference between both groups ($p=0.67$). From the researcher point of view may due to persistent pressure on body parts, which can reduce blood flow to tissue. These findings are supported by **Afzali Borojeny et al., (2020)** they showed that the most commonly affected area by pressure ulcer was sacrum, followed by buttocks, heels, and trochanters. **Mao and Zhu, (2021)** reported that sacrum and hip were the most prevalent locations of pressure ulcers with no statistically significant difference between the observation group and control group ($p=0.591$).

Results of the current study of stages shows that 85.7 % of the control and 33.3 % of study group were at stage II with statistically significant difference between both groups ($p=0.048$). From the researcher point of view, it is may be attributed to the routine hospital care which do not emphasize the importance of assessing skin regularly to detect early those at risk for developing pressure ulcers. This finding agreed with **Al-Mamari et al., (2024)** in study entitled "Hospital-acquired pressure ulcers among adult ICU patients in tertiary hospitals in Oman: a one-year prevalence study" who reported that the most common stage was stage 2 of PU. Also, **Zakaria et al. (2018)** found that approximately two thirds of the individuals had stage II pressure ulcers. In contrast to the control group, where the majority of patients had pressure ulcers in stages I, II, just two study subjects had stage I pressure ulcers, according to **Sugihara et al., (2018)**'s study.

Braden scale of the study groups

The mean total Braden scale was 15.20 ± 3.37 in control group and (16.22 ± 3.85) in the study group. This finding is supported by **Tayyib et al., (2015)** who reported that the mean Braden scale was 10.01 ± 1.53 in control group and 10.17 ± 2.23 in the study group with no statistically significant difference between both groups. **Hyun et al., (2013)** reported that ICU patients who had pressure ulcers develop had lower Braden scores 12.1 ± 2.5 than patients who did not have pressure ulcers develop 14.2 ± 3.7 .

Our study results show statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding mobility with more than half of control group and one third in study group slightly limited. From the researcher point of view the frequent positioning changes of patients every two hours reduced pressure, friction, and shear damage, and they experienced less extended pressure on bony prominences. This maintained a sufficient flow of oxygen and nutrients to the area and prevented tissue death. This

finding was consistent with that of **Sayed and Sliman, (2021)** who found statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding immobility with 37.9% of study group and 65.5% of control group had immobility. Repositioning the patient reduces the chance of pressure ulcer development and transfers or releases pressure on the areas that are vulnerable, according to another study by **Prakash & Prakash (2019)**. Repositioning is thought to shorten the time the tissue is subjected to pressure and lessen the risk of developing a pressure ulcer, according to a study by **Alimansur & Santoso, (2019)**

The present study results show statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding nutrition with 43.3% of control group and 56.7% in study group had adequate nutrition. From the researcher point of view nutrients, vitamins and minerals that support the formation of cell and tissue. This result agreed with that of **Sayed and Sliman, (2021)** who found statistically significant difference between control and study group regarding nutrition with 41.4% of study group and 17.2% of control group had malnutrition.

According to the results of the current study illustrate that there was a statistically significant difference between the study and control group regarding the total mean and SD of braden scale was 15.20 ± 3.67 in control group and (19.19 ± 2.6) in the study group, after application of the skin bundle intervention. Two weeks after the application of skin bundle interventions were put into place, the skin around bony prominent areas were reassessed. It was found that the interventions had been successful in protecting the skin. The researcher opinion that this may be attributed to the routine hospital care which do not emphasize the importance of assessing patients' skin regularly to detect early those at risk for developing pressure ulcers and do not institute appropriate measures to prevent this problem. This match with **Sayan et al., (2020)** who reported that, since all patients in the two groups had no risk of pressure ulcer on admission to the hospital the risk for pressure ulcer increased significantly after two weeks of the implementation of the nursing interventions among patients in the control group compared to those in the study group where the majority still have no risk.

CONCLUSION

According to the finding of this study, the study concludes that:

- 33% of Study group and 85.7% of control group had stage II pressure ulcer after intervention
- There was statistically significant difference between study and control group after the skin care bundle application.

Application of skin integrity care bundle was successfully significant reduction of developing of pressure ulcer in the intervention group of critically ill patients. It is playing a major role in protecting patients from developing pressure ulcer and prevent complications associated with ulcer.

Recommendations:

On the basis of the present study, the study recommended that:

- Encourage critical care nurses to join conferences and workshops to improve their knowledge and practice of application care bundles.
- Prior to policy changes, educate staff on new standards for evaluating, tracking, preventing, and treating skin breakdown. Ideally, the opinion leader would provide education on all new policy changes and requirements.

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